

Cosa (Ansedonia) in maps of global terrain elevations

Sparavigna, A. C.

Department of Applied Science and technology, Polytechnic University of Turin

Here we propose some information about topography and planimetric orientation of the Latin colony of Cosa, in Tuscany. Besides Mapy.cz, topography is also coming from it-ch.topographic-map.com, based on the research work by Yamazaki et al., 2017. The planimetry is discussed in the framework of supposed solar orientations of ancient Italic sites and of a presumed existence of a meridian axis at Cosa. Directions of sunrise on winter solstice and moonrise on major lunar standstill are also proposed on the map of Cosa.

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E. F. Brown tells us, in *The Princeton Encyclopedia of Classical Sites*, that Cosa (Ansedonia) in Etruria, was a Latin colony located on a rocky promontory of the Tyrrhenian coast, 139 km NW of Rome. The colony was founded in 273 B.C. after seizing its territory from Etruscan Vulci, as reported by Velleius Paterculus, Livy and Strabo (Brown, 1976). According to Livy, Cosa “prospered until an unrecorded event of the 60s B.C.”, that “left it sacked, burnt, and depopulated”. Under Augustus, Cosa was partially rebuilt, and survived for a while as a local religious and festival center, and then, in ruins, its forum was occupied by the center of a large estate (Brown, 1976). Modern excavations have surveyed the city plan, the principal buildings, and its port, and have also uncovered the Arx. In Cosa, “no trace of theater or amphitheater has been found” (Brown, 1976). The colony center was surrounded by fortifications of massive polygonal masonry. “The circuit of less than 2 km had curtains flanked by 18 square towers and was pierced by three gateways and a postern. The gateways were of the inner court type with arched outer openings closed by portcullises and inner gates” (Brown, 1976). Let us continue with the description of the site (see also Fig.1). “The town site, sloping northward, covered ca. 13 ha. Its principal features were twin summits with a level saddle between. Temples stood on the summits. The forum occupied the saddle. Main streets at right angles crossed the site from the gates and were directed at the forum and temple heights. Secondary streets ending in a pomerial road subdivided the site into rectangular and trapezoidal blocks” (Brown, 1976).

Fig.1: Cosa in a 3D map, courtesy of Mapy.cz. We can appreciate the sloping of the site.

For the topography, after the Brown's description and the 3D view, let us consider a recently proposed topographic map. The map is kindly provided by the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>. Terrain elevation is according to data coming from the research work by Yamazaki et al., in their article entitled "A high accuracy map of global terrain elevations", published in the Geophysical Research Letters, 2017. Let us report some words from the abstract of the article by Yamazaki et al., 2017. "Spaceborne digital elevation models (DEMs) are fundamental input for many geoscience studies, but they still include nonnegligible height errors. [In Yamazaki et al., 2017, the researchers] introduce a high accuracy global DEM at 3" resolution (~90 m at the equator) by eliminating major error components from existing DEMs".

The researchers "separated absolute bias, stripe noise, speckle noise, and tree height bias using multiple satellite data sets and filtering techniques. After the error removal, land areas mapped with ± 2 m or better vertical accuracy were increased from 39% to 58%. Significant improvements were found in flat regions where height errors larger than topography variability, and landscapes such as river networks and hill-valley structures, became clearly represented. ... The newly developed DEM will enhance many geoscience applications which are terrain dependent" (Yamazaki et al., 2017). Of course, the proposed DEM is proper for studies of geoscience. However, it is also useful for investigating local landscapes, and some applications have been previously proposed, for instance, in Sparavigna, 2021, 2022.

In the following Fig.2, we can see the site of Cosa.

Fig.2: Map of Cosa, from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com> (Many thanks to this web site).

Let us repeat the Brown's words: "Its principal features were twin summits with a level saddle between. ... The forum occupied the saddle", as clearly shown in the elevation map. In the map we can see the position of the Arx (Capitolium of Cosa), that, "on the loftier summit at the S angle of the fortifications, was set off from the city by low cliffs and walls of polygonal masonry" (Brown, 1976).

"At a broad opening on the *NE front a main street widened to become a sacred way*. The Arx came to be the seat of a major temple, the Capitolium (175-150 B.C.) and a minor, of Mater Matuta (?) (200-175 B.C.). The Capitolium, raised on a high podium above the terraced altar court, ... Under the floor of the Capitolium, on the crest of the summit, were found the traces of the *augural templum* and *sacred pit* which celebrated the inauguration of the colony. Behind the Capitolium, cuttings in the rock have disclosed the outlines of the first temple on the Arx (240-220 B.C.), dedicated to Jupiter and torn down when the major temple was built. A small building, later erected on the site of its altar court and composed of atrium, meeting rooms, and kitchen, testifies to the observances of a religious confraternity and to the life of the Arx during the Empire" (Brown, 1976).

Other literature is telling the following about Cosa and its orientation.

About the planimetry of Cosa, in Magli, 2007, it is told: "The interior of the city was planned on the basis of a rigid orthogonal grid, and this grid is in accordance with the disposition of the gates, so that – although no internal axis can be defined *Cardus* or *Decumanus*, because none of them connects two gates – the hippodamean layout might reasonably be considered contemporary with the construction of the walls (fig. 17a)". As we can clearly see from the topography, the streets have been arranged accordingly. The position of the gates is coherent with topography and streets orientation. For what is concerning the orientation of *Decumanus* and *Cardo*, a detailed discussion was given by Le Gall (Le Gall, 1975, Sparavigna, 2020).

Magli continues telling: "Curiously enough, however, it seems that the design was inspired from its very conception by a tripartite division of the urban space. First of all, the city had only three main gates (further to these, there is only one postern, located near the Acropolis). Second, during the excavation of the main temple on the Acropolis, the Capitolium dedicated to the Triade Capitolina, a squared basement, *roughly oriented to the cardinal points*, was discovered (fig. 18)". From the Fig.18, it seems that there is a misfit of 12 degrees. It is true that "roughly" means "approximately but not exactly", however 12 degrees are a non-negligible difference. Let us consider the diameter of the moon as seen from Earth. It is of 0.52 degrees. It means that the misfit of 12 degrees has approximately an angular size of 24 aligned moons. Magli is also telling that "The basement is of course more ancient than the temple above it, and it almost certainly refers to the first phase of construction of the town. At a few meters behind the basement, on axis with it and at the very center of the temple's cells, a natural rocky cleft was found; this probably contained a foundation deposit of first produce [Brown 1980]. Thus, *the archaeologists probably found in this the mundus of the city*, but it does not correspond to a geometrical center of the town's orthogonal grid, since the Acropolis lies in a spectacular position at the southern corner of the city walls, dominating the sea behind". We have previously seen that Brown is mentioning the *augural templum* (*auguranculum*) and the *sacred pit* (*mundus*). *Mundus* and *augural templum* are two different religious things. The *templum* is the *augural space* on terrain, which has a link with the quadripartition of the *augural sky*.

In Alcaide, 2013, in the Fig. 5, we can see the *auguranculum* and the *mundus* as given by Brown et al., 1960. Alcaide tells that "En opinión de Brown (Brown et al., 1960:13), el espacio cuadrado no estaba orientado ni a los puntos cardinales ni con los ejes de los planos de la ciudad, su orientación parece haber estado marcada más por un punto delimitado en el horizonte inmediato. ... La línea de visión, que continuaba hacia el norte, pasaba sobre la grieta, se proyectaba sobre la zona más plana de la ciudad hasta una pequeña elevación, fuera de ella, que se denomina actualmente Poggio dei Venti; en dirección opuesta hacia el sur se pierde en el mar; hacia el este seguiría la línea de costa y

hacia el oeste recogería los acantilados al pie de la colina y se prolongaría hacia la península del Argentario. Esto supondría que el cuadrado establece un punto de observación, un templum, que en su lado norte abarcaría la ciudad. A su vez las líneas diagonales que parten de las esquinas siguen la misma orientación que los decumani y los kardines así como su prolongación en la centuriación del territorio. Estos elementos que hemos descrito conformarían el primer lugar sagrado de la colonia y punto neurálgico del ritual de fundación. La gran plataforma cuadrada sería el auguraculum de Cosa, mientras la grieta natural justo delante de éste se correspondería con el mundus donde los primeros colonos depositaron sus ofrendas” (Alcaide, 2013).

Magli, 2007, notes that the mundus of the city “does not correspond to a geometrical center of the town’s orthogonal grid”, and then he is posing a question: “Thus, how should it be interpreted? If we ignore for a moment the orthogonal grid on which the streets of Cosa were laid out, the mundus actually turns out to have a geometrical function: the lines connecting it with the two northern doors divide the city in three quarters which are very similar in size, and, in addition, the line pointing to the north-west gate is oriented on the meridian (fig. 17b)” (Magli, 2007). And it seems being so, in the given Fig.17b by Magli.

At the link https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cosa#/media/File:Cosa_map.jpg we can find a map of Cosa, a work by Udimu. Many thanks to this contributor for providing the work under the CC BY-SA 4.0. Comparing with the map at the web page of JSTOR, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3293104>, in the publication entitled “Cosa: Republican Colony in Etruria”, The Classical Journal, 1949, we can verify the same orientation. Then, we can easily compare the line directions from the Arx to the Gates and the meridian direction.

Fig. 3: Map of Cosa. The red lines are the directions as given by Magli, 2007, in his Fig. 17, with a caption telling that “two solid lines have been drawn to connect the mundus of the city, in the central cell of the Capitolium, with the two north gates”. During the augurium of a colony, it was the augural space (auguranculum), not the mundus, to have possible links with special directions.

In Alcaide, 2013, about the foundation of Cosa, and the tripartition of its internal space, we can find told the following.

“En el ejemplo cosano, Brown (1951:26) señaló que los kardines siguen una orientación de 39° norte y los decumani de 51° respecto al norte. Sin embargo, otros estudios realizados por investigadores como Le Gall (1975:287-320) o G. Magli (2008:63-71) han puesto en relación la orientación de las ciudades antiguas romanas con la posición del Sol y la astronomía, aunque desde puntos de vista distintos. Por su parte Le Gall estableció una latitud de 42° 45' para Cosa. ... Por otro lado, Magli (2007:85-87) estudia el caso cosano en una comparativa con las ciudades de Ferentino, Alatri y Norba. Respecto a Cosa deduce que no es adecuado hablar de cardo y decumano máximo en la colonia ya que ninguno de ellos comunica de forma directa dos puertas. En relación con ello, una de las características del trazado urbano de Cosa es su kardo en bayoneta y a diferencia de otros de los casos que analiza considera que el trazado urbano es coetáneo con la construcción de la muralla. La tesis principal de su investigación radica en la tripartición de los espacios y en la existencia de una serie de características urbanísticas basadas en el número 3. Aprecia la reiteración de este uso en la construcción de tres puertas de acceso y en segundo lugar en la existencia del Capitolio dedicado a la Tríada Capitolina. Finalmente menciona el mundus excavado por el equipo americano de F. E. Brown hallado bajo el Capitolio y se observa que si trazamos unas líneas desde éste con las puertas noroeste y noreste, la ciudad queda dividida en tres partes de un tamaño similar. Las conclusiones de este trabajo invitan a pensar que en el mundo romano no sólo se utilizó el plano ortogonal sino que existían otras soluciones basadas en un urbanismo de división radial o triangular que tienen su origen en tradiciones más antiguas, probablemente del mundo griego arcaico o incluso micénico, y que serían transmitidas por los etruscos. En [Alcaide's] opinión, si bien consideramos que los preceptos rituales tuvieron que tener una determinada influencia en el urbanismo romano, sin embargo para Cosa no apreciamos de forma tan clara la tripartición del espacio y el urbanismo radial que expresa Magli, sobre todo en el trazo de líneas con las puertas orientadas al norte para dividir el espacio intramuros obviando por otro lado la puerta sureste, además como hemos expresado anteriormente éstas se sitúan en los puntos topográficos más favorables y que imposibilitan que el cardo y el decumano principal siguiesen un trazado recto” (Alcaide, 2013).

We need to add also the following observations from Alcaide, 2013, about the auguranculum. “Sin embargo no todos coinciden en la asimilación de estas estructuras con la sede inaugural de la colonia. De Magistris (2007:40) sostiene que las evidencias para determinar que la plataforma encontrada en el arx (fig. 5) se identifica con el auguraculum son muy escasas y generan más interrogantes que resolución de problemas. ... Este autor sin embargo plantea que debido a estas pruebas tan exiguas podría tratarse también de un área de extracción de piedra que se justificaría en los momentos iniciales de la ciudad para la obtención de material para la construcción y para ampliar el área constructiva del arx. Igualmente pone en duda que la gruta donde se encontraron restos de cenizas coincida con el mundus ya que este espacio había sido alterado antes de su excavación (De Magistris, 2007:47-48)” (Alcaide, 2013).

About the gates, “siguiendo la línea de la muralla hay una vaguada que desciende en su punto más bajo a una cota de unos 90 m aproximadamente, siendo en este punto exacto donde se construyó la puerta sureste también conocida como Porta Marina. Esta puerta junto con la puerta NE (Porta Romana) y la puerta NO (Porta Fiorentina) se establecen donde la topografía es más favorable, en las zonas más bajas y con mejor conexión con el exterior” (Alcaide, 2013).

Since we have mentioned the work by Le Gall on the orientation of the planimetry of Cosa, and since his work was about the solar orientation of ancient towns, that is of their decumani with the sunrise, let us consider the rising and setting of the sun at Cosa, on winter solstice (and also the southernmost rising direction of the moon on a major lunar standstill). The horizon is considered as the astronomical one.

Fig. 4: Sunrise and sunset directions on winter solstice, as given by the Suncalc.org software.

Fig. 5: Moonrise and moonset on a major lunar standstill, as given by the Mooncalc.org software.

Comparing Figs. 4 and 5, we can tell that we have a street “roughly oriented” to the sunrise on winter solstice, but we have, for the same street, a better orientation with the moonrise. If we consider an astronomical orientation, it is the moon which seems playing a major role.

The work by J. Le Gall on the solar orientation of the Roman camps, towns and centuriation, is concerning a detailed analysis of the ancient literature regarding this orientation. The article, published in 1975, is a fundamental reading so as not to get biased by any suggestion about solar orientation, that we can find in modern literature. Moreover, in recent literature, it is not easy to find the origin of the theory which is proposing the Decumanus oriented to the sunrise (or moonrise) on peculiar days, simply because it is not mentioned. After a detailed investigation of literature, I determined the origin in the *Das Templum*, 1869, a book by Heinrich Nissen. German professor of ancient history, Nissen studied the orientations of Egyptian and Greek temples and the orientations of churches too. In his *Das Templum*, we can

find his thought that the decumani of the towns were oriented to sunrise on the foundation day. He proposed to compare sunrise and decumanus azimuths to find this day. Moreover, he linked the foundation day to Roman festivals. Let us conclude adding that the Nissen's theory, which was based on the supposition that the ancient town were a templum, had been criticized in the past with strong arguments. In the References, references about Nissen's Das Templum are given and further literature about Cosa added.

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